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URANIUM IN ROCKS AS A SOURCE OF NATURAL RADIATION

Humanity today is particularly concerned with issues related to uranium and natural radiation. The purpose of the study is to provide a detailed overview of natural radioactivity, to analyze sources of natural radioactivity and natural uranium, and to characterize the impact of uranium on human life.

Natural Radioactivity. Radioactivity is an integral part of our environment. All living beings have been exposed to a constant flux of natural radiation on the surface of our friendly planet: to no negative effect. [1] A person cannot see, feel, hear, taste, or smell the ionizing radiation, but it can harm our health. This type of radiation comes from natural sources, such as cosmic radiation, rocks, or soil. Radiation sources can also be artificial sources, such as the use of certain industrial and medical technologies. The impact of natural radiation on humans is the cause of a number of certain pathogenic mutations and cancers. [2] Rocks like granite, which have become symbols of permanence and durability, contain light traces of radioactive uranium. Even the food we eat or the air we breathe contains radioactive elements – either formed thanks to the intervention of cosmic rays, or as old as the solar system itself.

The most important natural source of radioactivity is a rare gas known as radon. One of the products of uranium decay, radon is an ‘inert gas’ that can participate in no chemical reaction. This would seem to make it completely harmless, were it not for the fact that radon own radioactive decay produces gases poisonous to humans. The nature of the soil you live on, the construction tools used to build your house and the quality of its air conditioning are all crucial factors in determining radon exposure.

Natural Uranium. The primordial uranium found ubiquitously in nature consists of two isotopes with mass numbers of 235 and 238. In the earth's crust, 238U constitutes 99.27% of the uranium by mass, and 235U, the parent isotope of the actinium chain, 0.72%. 234U, a shorter-lived member of the 238 U chain, is usually in radioactive equilibrium or near-equilibrium with the parent isotope. Occurrence and Doses Uranium is found in all rocks and soils. In the common rock types, the uranium concentrations range from 0.5 to 4.7 ppm, corresponding to activity concentrations for 238U of 7-60 Bq/kg (0.2-1.6 pCi/g). The overall effect of soil development results in an average soil concentration of uranium less than the average rock concentration. Some ores mined and processed for nonradioactive materials can produce residues with elevated concentrations of radionuclides. Natural materials that contain uranium at over 500 ppm are considered to be uranium ores. [3]

Uranium Minerals: There are Primary (Hypogenic), Secondary (Relict) and Hypergenic minerals. Among the most important minerals of uranium are: Uraninite (62-85%), Nasturan (52-76%), Uranium black (11-53%), % - the content of uranium. Uraninite (sideways) refers to primary (hypogenic) minerals. The most famous type of Uraninite is sideways (uranium tar, uranium tar ore). In many fields it is the main ore

mineral, in particular it is predominant in uranium-bearing alkaline metasomatites among the ferruginous rocks of the Northern Kryvyi Rih region, but is less widespread in comparison with uraninite, brannerite, and albites. This species is characterized by spherulitic, renal, concentric, zonal-striped structures and their variations.

Uranium ferrous is a secondary (relic) mineral. Uranium blacks are part of powdered earthy masses and cement breccias that fill the cracks of mother rocks. The ideal formula corresponds to uraninite with $UO_2 < UO_3$ and significant water content. [4]

Conclusion. Natural radioactivity is the principal source of radiation exposure. Rocks like granite contain light traces of radioactive uranium. The most important natural source of radioactivity is a rare gas known as radon. The impact of natural radiation on humans is the cause of a number of certain pathogenic mutations and cancers.

References

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